

3D Quantitative Intracellular Visualization of Graphene Oxide Nanoparticles by Tomographic Flow Cytometry

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ABSTRACT. Interaction of nanoparticles (NPs) with cells is of fundamental importance in biology and biomedical sciences. NPs can be taken up by cells, thus interacting with their intracellular elements, modifying the life cycle pathways and possibly inducing death. Therefore, there is a great interest in understanding and visualizing the process of cellular uptake itself or even secondary effects, e.g. toxicity. Nowadays, no methods are reported yet in which 3D imaging of NPs distribution can be achieved for suspended cells in flow-cytometry. Here we show that, by means of label-free tomographic flow-cytometry, it is possible to obtain full 3D quantitative spatial distribution of nano-graphene oxide (nGO) inside each single flowing cell. This can allow setting a class of biomarkers that characterize the 3D spatial intracellular deployment of nGO or other NPs clusters, thus opening the route for quantitative descriptions to discover new insights in the realm of NP-cell interactions.

In the last decades, nano-graphene and its derivatives have captured much attention due to their superb electronic properties^{1,2} and promising applications in biomedicine field, even including approaches to fight or detect infections caused by the new coronavirus SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19)^{3,4}. Indeed, graphene and graphene oxide (GO) have been used in making DNA-based optical sensors for drug delivery⁵ and for the detection of nucleic acids⁶, proteins⁷, virus⁸, metal ions⁹ and small molecules¹⁰. Furthermore, nGO is a promising candidate as vaccine carrier and adjuvant for efficient intracellular vaccine protein delivery¹¹⁻¹³. Different techniques are continuously developed and refined to study the interactions of Graphene Family Materials (GFMs) with biological samples. The cell proliferation assay (MTT) is used for the nonradioactive, spectrophotometric quantification of cell proliferation, viability in cell populations and in vitro toxicology¹⁴. Careful validation of MTT assay procedures is needed in experiments where GFMs are one of the constituents, to avoid a potential bias in concluding results of cytotoxicity studies¹⁵. In fact, GO is a universal fluorescence quencher^{11,16}. Hence, the use of fluorescence techniques for revealing, quantifying and visualizing GO can be affected by the fluorescent quenching due to the interactions of NPs with fluorophores and organic dyes¹⁷. Thus, fluorescence-based methods are not suitable for toxicity testing of carbon-based nanomaterials. Another gold standard technique to study nanomaterials-cells interaction or even mapping the GO intracellular distribution exploits electron-based microscopy, such as Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). Recently, many interesting developments have been achieved about other imaging modalities for measuring intracellular processes. A new photoconvertible fluorescent protein to assure high resolution and large field of view for imaging dynamic movements of the endoplasmic reticulum by a confocal microscope was used¹⁸. The processes of endosomal membrane uptake and release of fluorescent nanodiamond-gold NPs was elucidated by multimodal optical-electron imaging¹⁹. A hybrid

Raman fluorescence spectral imaging method for single-cell microscopy uses was disclosed²⁰. Proof of snapshot acquisition allowing simultaneous 3D tracking of many fluorescent particles was shown²¹. Imaging of intracellular processes was reported by a fluorescent microresonator fully enclosed into a live cell²². Photon upconversion scheme using nanoparticles for super-resolution imaging was investigated²³. Confocal Raman imaging for tracking the nGO cellular uptake in living cells avoiding any additional fluorescent or plasmonic tag was also reported²⁴. However, all the above mentioned methods and many others provide imaging and measurements in cells but very few studies were devoted to visualize the 3D spatial distribution of NP uptake in cells in quantitative way. Confocal microscopy would be the elective optical tool to this aim, but, as mentioned before, fluorescent quenching strongly limits GO imaging. Moreover, while it is quite easy to perform 3D confocal scanning of cells on a flat surface, it is impossible on suspended cells or in flow-cytometry. Flow cytometry is a technology particularly suited to provide a quantitative measurement of the cellular uptake of NPs²⁵⁻²⁸. Sample preparation is fast and simple, and statistically relevant results can be obtained because of its high-throughput property. In particular, a flow cytometer measures the scattering and fluorescence signals of single cells in flow. The side scattering has been correlated to the cellular granularity^{25,26}, but it has a low sensibility, because it is generated both from the internalized NPs and the NPs attached on the cellular surface, its values depend on the kind of NP and its variations are also influenced by changes in the cell morphology and/or viability^{26,28}. Hence, the fluorescence signal of labelled NPs provides a more robust analysis^{26,27}, but fluorescent tags can influence the particle properties and behavior²⁶ and the fluorescence signal must be calibrated to provide an absolute value of the NP uptake²⁸. Digital Holography (DH) has been recently adopted as a valuable full-field, label-free, non-invasive and high-resolution tool for nanomaterial toxicity and cell interaction studies by morphologic

characterization^{29,30}. In fact, biophysical and morphological parameters such as cell volume, thickness, density, dry mass, refractive index (RI) variation in time and bio-distribution of NPs inside cell cytoplasm can be measured by phase-contrast images, without the use of chemical compounds that could interfere with nanomaterials. Ability of DH to evaluate the bio-distribution of nGO internalized in adhered live cells for 24 h and 48 h has been demonstrated³¹. Nonetheless, a strong limitation still exists in understanding the real 3D spatial distribution within adhered cells³¹. In fact, in the previous studies, analysis was limited to two-dimensional (2D) spatial distribution of nGO²⁹. On the other side, very interesting results have been presented in the DH framework by introducing a genetically encodable phase-contrast agent based on gas vesicles to enhance the contrast inside cells³². To achieve a full 3D visualization of flowing cells, Tomographic Flow Cytometry (TFC) by DH has been demonstrated to measure the morphological parameters of red blood cells, marine algae (i.e. diatoms)³³ and circulating tumour cells³⁴. However, nGO and their aggregates strongly scatter visible light, therefore phase-contrast microscopy cannot be effective in retrieving their 3D spatial distribution. To overcome this issue, here we propose and demonstrate for the first time, to the best of our knowledge, an alternative strategy to perform in-flow cyto-tomography by DH for revealing the 3D spatial intracellular distribution of nGO. Thanks to the ability of DH in automatically retrieving 3D positions and viewing angles of flowing and rotating cells along a microfluidic channel, we demonstrate that a 3D tomogram can be obtained by using the amplitude maps computed from the recorded digital holograms, thus furnishing an intriguing complete visualization in 3D of internalized nGO aggregates. In particular, we show how the 3D spatial distribution of nGO changes in different fibroblast cells for two cell culture times, i.e. 24 h and 48 h. Moreover, we compare qualitatively our results with a well-established method to estimate the 3D shape of a sample, namely Shape

From Silhouette (SFS)³⁵. We show that the proposed technique allows for a much more detailed reconstruction of the 3D nGO distribution if compared to SFS. Our results open the route for high-throughput investigation at single cell level thanks to the proofed ability to operate with flow-cytometry. Thus it will be possible to provide statistically relevant investigations on a large number of cells for understanding how internalized nGO distributes inside each cell. In fact, as cellular populations are heterogeneous and single-cell therapies necessarily require non-destructive (i.e. label-free) characterization methods, only a flow cytometry approach can allow thorough information on interaction of nGO at intracellular scale. Moreover, it is noteworthy that the method can be extended without loss of generality to different classes of NPs, thus becoming a powerful 3D imaging tool at flow-cytometric scale. To date, the investigation of statistically relevant numbers of living cells in non-destructive manner remains unaddressed, leaving the basic problem of NPs-cell interactions realm still almost unexplored in a 3D scenario at single cell level. Thus, the approach and results presented in this study can furnish a novel analysis tool to address new knowledge about this issue.

Figure 1. (Supporting Movie 1) 2D imaging of NIH-3T3 cells. (a) Inverted microscope image of an NIH-3T3 cell after 48 h from the nGO adding in DMEM medium. The internalized nGO (black) distributes around nucleus. Scale bar is 10 μm . (b) Sketch of the opto-fluidic recording system based on a DH microscope in off-axis configuration. BSF, Beam Splitter Fiber; MP, Microfluidic Pump; MC, Microfluidic Channel; OB, Object Beam; MO, Microscope Objective; BE, Beam Expander; RB, Reference Beam; BC, Beam Combiner; PC, Personal Computer. (c) Five cuts of digital holograms of the same NIH-3T3 cell at different time frames after 24 h from the nGO adding in DMEM medium. Cell flows along y-axis and rotates around x-axis. Scale bar is 20 μm .

Murine embryonic fibroblasts NIH-3T3 were chosen to analyse the effects of nGO *in-vitro*. The cell culture was monitored at 24 h and 48 h, as shown by the inverted microscope images in Fig. 1(a) and Figs. S1(a,b). At time points of 24 h and 48 h, cells were detached by trypsin-EDTA and injected into a microfluidic channel to collect images of flowing cells through a DH microscope, sketched in Fig. 1(b). More details about cell culture and the imaging setup are reported in the Supporting Information. In Fig. 1(c), we show five cuts taken from the recorded holographic sequence of a flowing and rotating NIH-3T3 cell after a treatment of 24 h with nGO. The holographic reconstruction processing based on the angular spectrum method is employed to obtain the in-focus complex wavefront, from which the Amplitude Map (AM) and the Quantitative Phase Map (QPM) are recovered³⁷. For each flowing and rotating cell, the Phase Contrast TFC (PC-TFC) reconstruction can be performed by calculating both their 3D positions and orientations. In particular, 3D positions within the micro-channel are retrieved through a holographic tracking algorithm³⁸. Each ROI containing the analysed cell in the in-focus QPM sequence is realigned in the corresponding transversal position to avoid tomographic motion artefacts. Then, the unknown viewing angles, that correspond to the cell rolling angles, are estimated by using the computed 3D positions and exploiting the image similarity through local contrast image measurements³⁹. More details about the TFC processing pipeline are reported in the Supporting Information. Finally, the realigned images and the retrieved orientations are used as inputs of the Filtered Back Projection (FBP) algorithm^{33,34} to reconstruct the 3D RI tomogram of the analysed cell.

Figure 2. (Supporting Movies 2-4) 3D graphene reconstruction through PC-TFC and AM-TFC methods in three NIH-3T3 cells after 24h-treatment with nGO. (a,f,k) ROIs containing the NIH-3T3 cells in the recorded digital holograms, in which the accumulation of internalized nGO has a disruptive effect on the interference fringe pattern (blue insert). (b,g,l) Numerically retrieved QPMs, with highlighted in the red insert the dark spot due to graphene disturbance in the recorded holograms in (a,f,k). (c,h,m) Isolevels representation of the 3D PC-TFC reconstructions. In (c,h), the nGO

accumulation (black) is segmented and isolated from the outer cell (red), while this is not possible in (m). (d,i,n) Numerically retrieved AMs, with highlighted in the green insert the dark spot due to graphene disturbance in the recorded holograms in (a,f,k). (e,j,o) Isolevels representation of the 3D AM-TFC reconstructions, in which the nGO accumulation (black) is segmented and isolated from the outer cell (green). Scale bars are 10 μm . The intervals highlighted in the colorbars refer to the inserts.

Unlike cells, nGO is a strong scattering material in the visible spectrum, which causes alterations within the periodic interference fringe pattern recorded by DH. When the amount of internalized graphene is low, this disruptive phenomenon is localized in a little region within the cell, as highlighted in Figs. 2(a,f,k) by the blue inserts within the digital holograms of three NIH-3T3 cells treated with nGO for 24 h, respectively. The effect of nGO can be observed as a dark spot in the red inserts within the retrieved QPMs shown in Figs. 2(b,g,l). Moreover, this dark spot appears in several images of the QPM sequence, changing its position every time because of the cell rotation. After performing the PC-TFC reconstruction on first two cells in Fig. 2, the 3D visualization of accumulated nGO is obtained by setting a suitable threshold that allows its recognition at the lowest RI values, as shown in Figs. 2(c,h) by black regions within the red cell shells (see also Supporting Movies 2-3). Instead, a different experimental situation is reported in the cell in Figs. 2(k-o), where the nGO accumulation has caused phase discontinuities within QPMs of the same sequence. This behaviour provokes distortions of the reconstructed tomogram, thus making the visualization of nGO grains unfeasible. In fact, in Fig. 2(m) the PC-TFC reconstruction lacks the nGO cluster, even if the corresponding QPM in Fig. 2(l) clearly shows graphene internalization. To overcome this drawback, we propose a new method to reconstruct the 3D tomogram, exploiting AMs instead of QPMs. Figures 2(d,i,n) show the AMs for the three test

cases, respectively, in which the nGO grains are still visible in any image of the sequence but without discontinuities as in the corresponding QPMs (see also Supporting Movie 4). We implement the FBP algorithm with the AMs as input along with viewing angles calculated by using the rolling angles recovery method explored for PC-TFC. Therefore, we can refer to the proposed method as AM-TFC. While in PC-TFC the reconstructed tomogram is the quantitative 3D spatial distribution of cell RI, in AM-TFC we can only claim that the reconstructed tomogram is a 3D visualization of intracellular regions having different light attenuation coefficients. However, unlike PC-TFC, the AM-TFC reconstruction allows the identification of the 3D graphene spatial distribution within NIH-3T3 cell at its lowest values also in the third analysed test case, as reported in Fig. 2(o). Moreover, as proof of the effectiveness of the proposed approach, the AM-TFC reconstructions about other two test cases in Figs. 2(e,j) can be compared with the PC-TFC ones in Figs. 2(c,h), respectively, showing remarkable similarities. Here, it is worth pointing out that the higher the quantity of internalized nGO, the less the ability to provide an effective PC-TFC reconstruction. Therefore, with very high nGO internalization, the proposed reconstruction method is decisive to detect the 3D spatial distribution of nGO within cells. To prove this, we also study a NIH-3T3 cell after a 48h-treatment, in which a massive nGO internalization can be observed. This is evident in the four frames taken from the recorded holographic sequence displayed in Fig. 3(a). Graphene has arranged as a ring within the cell around the nucleus (nuclear decoration^{27,31}), thus occupying a large cell volume. Consequently, phase retrieval fails for any hologram of the sequence, since many phase discontinuities occur, thus preventing the PC-TFC reconstruction, as displayed in Fig. 3(b). This is due to light losing coherence while passing through the highly absorbing nGO cluster within the cell.

Figure 3. (Supporting Movie 5) 3D graphene reconstruction in an NIH-3T3 cell after 48h-treatment with nGO. (a) Four frames taken from the recorded holographic sequence of the rolling cell, from which a ring-shaped nGO spatial distribution can be inferred. (b) QPMs numerically retrieved from (a), in which the phase jumps are not corrected by the unwrapping algorithm. (c) AMs numerically retrieved from (a), in which the dark regions are due to the light attenuation of the internalized graphene. (d,e) Three views of the isolevels representation of the tomogram reconstructed through SFS and AM-TFC algorithms, respectively, in which the internalized nGO (black), segmented and isolated from the outer cell (yellow and green, respectively), distributes as a 3D ring, as observed in 2D images in (a-c). Scale bar in (a) is 10 μm . In (a-c), the estimated viewing angles are reported at the top.

Instead, the dark ring region is properly preserved in the AMs in Fig. 3(c), thus the AM-TFC approach is able to recover the 3D visualization of internalized nGO with high accuracy, as shown by three different views of the AM-TFC reconstruction in Fig. 3(e). To further demonstrate the effectiveness of AM-TFC algorithm, we perform a comparison with a well-established 3D shape reconstruction method, namely SFS, already demonstrated to recover the 3D visualization of live cell⁴⁰. Here, the SFS algorithm is performed separately on the overall cell, to reconstruct the cell shell, and on the nGO distribution obtained from AMs. The result, reported in Fig. 3(d), clearly shows low resolution in defining the nGO shape if compared to the AM-TFC reconstruction in Fig. 3(e).

Figure 4. 3D quantitative Euclidean analysis from AM-TFC reconstructions of nGO uptake in NIH-3T3 cells after 24h-treatments. (a-c) AM-TFC reconstructions of three 24h-cells (green) and their nGO clusters (black). C is the cell centroid, G is the graphene centroid and M is the nearest point of the external cell membrane to point G . Line c joins points C and G and line m joins points M and G . Line g passes for point G and is orientated like 3D nGO cluster. (d) Cartesian plot of graphene-cell normalized distance $\delta(G,C)$ versus graphene-membrane normalized distance $\delta(G,M)$. (e) Cartesian plot of graphene sphericity Ψ_G versus graphene equivalent radius ρ_G . (f) Polar plot in which the radial coordinate is the graphene sphericity Ψ_G and the angular coordinate is the graphene-cell angle θ_{GC} . (g) Polar plot in which the radial coordinate is the graphene-cell normalized distance $\delta(G,C)$ and the angular coordinate is the graphene-cell angle θ_{GC} .

The tomographic results reported in Fig. 3 allow a much more complete understanding of the nGO internalization process in respect to the previous 2D methods³¹. In fact, by means of the approach presented here, a 3D visual analysis is immediately available, thus furnishing insights on how nGO is clustering and spatially distributing within the cell volume. Besides, beyond this very useful full 3D direct visualization, here we discuss how to extract quantitative 3D measurements for a full nGO characterization. These quantitative parameters can be the bases for the definition of biomarkers for nGO-cell interaction in terms of 3D spatial intracellular deploying of nGO. At the aim to define some 3D morphological parameters to investigate nGO positioning and shapes, we report again in Figs. 4(a-c) the AM-TFC reconstructions at 24 h of Figs. 2(e,j,o) and we name them cell 1, cell 2 and cell 3, respectively. In particular, we measure the graphene-cell normalized distance $\delta(G, C)$, the graphene-membrane normalized distance $\delta(G, M)$, the orientation of the detected nGO cluster (i.e. the graphene-cell angle θ_{GC}), its sphericity⁴¹ Ψ_G and its equivalent radius ρ_G . In all three cases, nGO clusters are about in the same relative position between cell centroid and cell membrane, as shown by the $\delta(G, C)$ versus $\delta(G, M)$ plot in Fig. 4(d), and moreover they are closer to the cell membrane, as displayed in Figs. 4(a-c). Their sphericity Ψ_G decreases with a bigger graphene equivalent radius ρ_G , as reported in Fig. 4(e), and with a bigger graphene-cell angle θ_{GC} , as shown by polar plot in Fig. 4(f). In addition, as also visible in Figs. 4(a-c), nGO clusters are oriented about orthogonally with respect to cell radius, but graphene-cell angle θ_{GC} slightly decreases with the graphene-cell normalized distance $\delta(G, C)$, as reported in the polar plot in Fig. 4(g). Hence, passing from 24 h to 48 h, as the volumes of nGO clusters increase, their sphericities reduce since they stretch orthogonally with respect to cell radius, in order to finally form a unique 3D ring structure, as visible in Fig. 3(e).

Figure 5. (Supporting Movie 5) 3D quantitative Euclidean analysis from AM-TFC reconstructions of nGO uptake in NIH-3T3 cells after 48h-treatments. (a) Modelled toroid (yellow) and 3D nGO ring structure (black) unrolled by converting the cartesian coordinates in spherical coordinates. In the insert, toroid used to model 3D nGO ring structure of the 48h-cell. C_T is the centre of the toroid and c_T is the centre of its generator circle (black), which radius is r_T (inner radius). The outer radius R_T is the distance between centres C_T and c_T . (b-d) Comparison between the histograms of the modelled toroid (yellow) and the 3D nGO ring structure (black) about the azimuthal angle, the elevation angle and the radial distance, respectively.

Furthermore, the test case reported in Fig. 3 needs a more sophisticated morphological analysis. We model the 3D shape of nGO in Fig. 3(e) as a toroid having its same volume, as shown by the inset in Fig. 5(a). The toroid provides a rough estimation of the nuclear size, since the 3D nGO ring distributes around nucleus without accessing it, because nGO particles are larger than the functional diameter of the nuclear pores³¹. This information is very valuable in a label-free technique such as DH, in which the intracellular identification is still an open and challenging issue, since no dyes are used to make nucleus visible and easily detachable from the surrounding cytoplasm. Moreover, the toroidal modelling can be exploited for an additional quantitative analysis about 3D nGO distribution by unrolling its shape through the conversion in spherical coordinates, i.e. azimuthal angle, elevation angle and radial distance, as reported in yellow in Fig. 5(a). We perform the same calculation on the nGO shape, reported in black in Fig. 5(a), enabling a quantitative evaluation about the surface irregularity through histograms of spherical coordinates in Figs. 5(b-d). A more detailed discussion about the geometrical analysis and visualization is provided in Supporting Information.

To summarize all the quantitative descriptors, in Table 1 we report a set of parameters that can be quantitatively measured from the AM-TFC reconstructions at 24 h and 48 h, including those described above. In particular, the graphene volume increases of two orders of size in passing from 24 h to 48 h. As a consequence, the cell equivalent radius grows by a few microns, since a large amount of graphene is internalized. These volumetric measurements could be very useful to study the cytotoxicity effects due to nGO uptake, for example to kill sick cells, such as tumour cells⁴².

Table 1. Quantitative measurements in AM-TFC reconstructions of three NIH-3T3 cells after 24 h and 48 h from the nGO adding in DMEM medium.

	24h - 1	24h - 2	24h - 3	48h
<i>Cell Volume [μm^3]</i>	6006.59	3053.92	3092.40	9478.44
<i>Cell Equivalent Radius [μm]</i>	11.28	9.00	9.04	13.13
<i>Graphene Volume [μm^3]</i>	12.10	8.66	13.25	2339.69
<i>Graphene Equivalent Radius [μm]</i>	1.42	1.27	1.47	8.24
<i>Graphene-Cell Volume Ratio [%]</i>	0.20	0.28	0.43	24.68
<i>Graphene Surface Area [μm^2]</i>	28.69	22.12	30.22	1933.38
<i>Graphene Sphericity [%]</i>	0.89	0.92	0.90	0.44
<i>Graphene 1st Principal Axis [μm]</i>	3.47	2.85	3.60	-
<i>Graphene 2nd Principal Axis [μm]</i>	2.90	2.47	2.64	-
<i>Graphene 3rd Principal Axis [μm]</i>	1.72	1.77	2.08	-
<i>Graphene-Cell Distance [μm]</i>	8.35	5.51	6.25	1.79
<i>Graphene-Membrane Distance [μm]</i>	2.90	3.38	2.64	-
<i>Graphene-Cell Normalized Distance [a.u.]</i>	0.74	0.62	0.70	-
<i>Graphene-Membrane Normalized Distance [a.u.]</i>	0.26	0.38	0.30	-
<i>Graphene-Cell Angle [deg]</i>	83.63	77.17	86.76	-
<i>Toroid Outer Radius [μm]</i>	-	-	-	9.88
<i>Toroid Inner Radius [μm]</i>	-	-	-	3.47
<i>Azimuthal Angle Percentage Error [%]</i>	-	-	-	24.40
<i>Elevation Angle Percentage Error [%]</i>	-	-	-	54.82
<i>Radial Distance Percentage Error [%]</i>	-	-	-	30.72

The 3D spatial intracellular distribution of NPs clusters has been easily achieved for the first time by means of a new tomography method in flow micro-cytometry device. We demonstrated that the 3D spatial distribution of internalized nGO cluster can be easily quantified by retrieving the 3D tomogram of flowing cells, thus opening the way to high-throughput single cell analysis. Reported proof-of-concept results show that a label-free, non-destructive and potentially fully automatic imaging technology is potentially able to provide statistically relevant assays on a large number of cells for better inferring new insights on how nGO gets internalized and distributes itself inside them. Indeed, as cellular populations are heterogeneous and single-cell studies necessarily require non-destructive and label-free characterization methods, only a flow cytometry approach can allow thorough information on interaction of nGO at intracellular scale.

Moreover, the method we proposed can be extended without loss of generality to different classes of NPs and other cells. The AM-TFC concept has been introduced to cope with the issue of correctly visualizing in 3D internalized particles, thus overcoming the limitations of PC-TFC due to harsh scattering processes and absorption-related artefacts. Finally, we proposed a new class of geometrical descriptors that could be the basis for setting quantitative 3D biomarkers to measure and classify NPs intracellular spatial distributions relying on the promising and still partially unexplored paradigm of 3D imaging at single-cell level, also applicable with high-throughput modality.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. The following files are available free of charge. Additional details on cell culture (with Fig. S1), tomographic flow cytometry by digital holography, 3D morphological inspection of nGO within cells (PDF).

Supporting Movie 1 - recorded DH sequence containing flowing and rotating NIH-3T3 cells (MP4).

Supporting Movie 2 - recorded DH sequence, numerically retrieved QPMs and AMs, slice by slice and isolevels representation of both PC-TFC and AM-TFC reconstructions with highlighted in black the 3D nGO cluster localized in an NIH-3T3 cell after a 24h-treatment (MP4).

Supporting Movie 3 - recorded DH sequence, numerically retrieved QPMs and AMs, slice by slice and isolevels representation of both PC-TFC and AM-TFC reconstructions with highlighted in black the 3D nGO cluster localized in an NIH-3T3 cell after a 24h-treatment (MP4).

Supporting Movie 4 - recorded DH sequence, numerically retrieved QPMs and AMs, slice by slice and isolevels representation of AM-TFC reconstruction with highlighted in black the 3D nGO cluster localized in an NIH-3T3 cell after a 24h-treatment, while it is not identifiable in PC-TFC reconstruction (MP4).

Supporting Movie 5 - recorded DH sequence after a 48h-treatment, numerically retrieved AMs, slice by slice and isolevels representations of AM-TFC reconstruction. The last part of the movie reports slice by slice and isolevels representations of the unrolled 3D nGO ring structure. The 3D nGO cluster localized in an NIH-3T3 cell is highlighted in black (MP4).

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Author Contributions

MM performed and was in charge for all the biological investigation and experiments supervised by SG. GCL and RC take care of the chemistry of nGO, preparation and characterization. FM

performed the holographic acquisitions. The DH setup was designed and arranged by FM and LM. DP and PM performed the numerical holographic process under the supervision of PM. DP, VB, PM, LM, PF discussed the tomographic results. Results were discussed by all the authors. All authors contributed to write the manuscript. PF supervised the research. ‡These authors contributed equally.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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